

A HIGH PERFORMANCE EPOXY MATRIX AND COMPOSITE FOR HELICOPTER ROTOR BLADES

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ABSTRACT

Advanced epoxy resin composites employing glass or carbon fiber reinforcement form the basis for many contemporary engineering structural designs, especially designs related to aerospace applications. Other industries requiring a high degree of reliability in their structural components also incorporate these lightweight materials into their cost-conscious designs.

This work had been obtained successfully the high performance epoxy matrix modified. The processing mechanical and thermal properties of the resin casting and its composite laminates were investigated considerably. The results show that the research resin system has the long working life, low viscosity and its composites are particularly good in elevated temperatures (120°C, 150°C) strength retention and fatigue resistance.

The resin matrix is suitable to fabricating the composite main rotor blades of helicopter specifically and industrial miscellaneous applications of composites too.

Keywords: Epoxy Matrix, Composite, Rotor Blade, Glass Roving, Glass Cloth, Carbon Fiber, mechanical Property, Heat Resistance.

INTRODUCTION

The composite rotor blades, as it is well known in the rotorcraft community, have matured to a powerful and economic dynamic aircraft structure, due to the performances inherent in composite materials. The high specific static and fatigue strength in combination with the ability of composite materials to "tailor" the mechanical properties are immediately evident^[1].

For a high performance composite, the high performance resin matrix, as well as the reinforcement fiber is requisite. Until recently most resin matrices of the advanced composites are the epoxy resin systems, that are used to cure with aromatic amine or dicyandiamide. The toughening component is generally a CTBN type elastomer. However, major drawbacks of this system are inherently brittle or sharp fall of the modulus at elevated temperature. They can not used in the primary structure part of aircraft^[2].

The resin matrix selected for fabrication of composite main rotor blades of the helicopter should have high modulus and strength at -40 — $+60^{\circ}\text{C}$, good processing properties such as long working life and low viscosity. It should also be inexpensive.

In order to meet demand of the structure design of the composite rotor blades, we chose and characterized a epoxy resin system modified by two toughening agents and two curing agents^[3].

EXPERIMENTAL

A typical bisphenol A diglycidyl ether E-51 was used for all the studies discussed in this paper. Three toughening components are bis-(2,3-epoxy-cyclopentyl) ether W-95, CTBN elastomer and fatty epoxide B-63. The hexahydro-phthalic anhydride (HHPA) as curing agent and the 2-ethyl-4-methylimidazole (EMI-2,4) as catalyst were used for all experiments. The textile reinforcements used in this study include the following: unidirectional roving of s-glass and E-glass, twill weave woven cloth of s-glass and plain weave woven cloth of s-glass (Nanjing Glass Fiber Research Institute). The carbon fiber used was moderate strength fiber (Shanghai Carbon Element Fub.). In this test all glass strand and cloth were treated by amino-silane coupling agent KH-550. The fiber reinforced laminates were fabricated by the hand-lay-up or half-dry (preperg) technique.

Tensile, flexural and short beam shear properties were measured according the references^[4-6]. An Instron type testing machine was employed in the experiments.

Heat deflection temperatures (HTD) of the cured resins were measured according to ASTM D648-56.

Infrared spectra were obtained using a Nicolet FTIR spectrometer (Model 5DX). The epoxy mixtures were placed between KBr crystals that were separated by a 0.5mm spacer for FTIR studies of the cure reactions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It must be remembered that composite rotor blades following more than 6000 hours of flight time show no degradation in their properties; metal rotor blades only have ca 1000 hours. The composite rotor blade structure and section of helicopter is shown in Figure 1.

The spectra of the epoxy resin, the HHPA and the EMI-2.4 mixtures heated at 120°C and 150°C for one hour are shown in Figure 2-A and 2-B, respectively. It is observed that the epoxy band at 915cm^{-1} is unchanged for the sample heated at 120°C, but the band disappeared for the sample heated at 150°C. The difference spectrum of these two samples shows that the peak of the ester group intensifies at 1620cm^{-1} .

The YEW-7808 matrix system was based on the mixture component of both E-51 and W-95 epoxy resins. The W-95 cycloaliphatic epoxide cured has high modulus, high elongation, high thermal resistance and very high fatigue resistance^[7].

The addition of W-95, CTBN and B-63 modified agents to epoxy matrices part improves the resin castings flexural strength. To determine the extent of these improvements, the performance of various contents of W-95, CTBN and B-63 was investigated. The resulting effect in casting flexural strength with increasing improvement level is seen in Figure 3. The flexural strength increases to a maximum for the three curves at 20-35%. At higher levels of modified agents the flexural strength decreases for CTBN, unchanges for B-63 and continues in increase for W-95. Therefore, W-95 is the best modified agent.

The bending fatigue test of the composites for the rotor blades had been performed. The regression curves S/N for a stress ration of $R=0.2$ are presented in figure 4. The results show that the delaminatons propagating of these specimens were prevented well.

Table 1 presents a comparison of five widely-used commercial fibre and textile reinforcements for the mechanical properties. YEW-7808 resin system has a much lower viscosity at 30°C but still not below 1000cps. The gel time at 80°C and RT physical properties are good, the HDT of 186°C is good. Property retention of YEW-7808 composite at 150°C is the best in comparison with these new resin systems (see Table 2 and 3).

For most structure composite applications, it is desirable to have the tensile elongation of the resin matrix be equal to or above that of the reinforcing fiber (about 2-1/2 to 3% for fiberglass). This allows load transfer from fiber-to-fiber with less tendency for matrix failure^[8]. It can be seen from figure 1 that the tensile elongation for YEW-7808 resin matrix had reached 4.4%.

The effect of temperature on the short beam shear and flexural properties of glass roving reinforced research epoxy matrices is shown in Tables 2 and 3. The strength retention at 150°C is excellent in both cases of YEW-7808 and YEB7912, besides YEN-8204.

CONCLUSION

The resin system modified by the W-95 epoxide and imidazole curing agent had been succeeded in use for the composite rotor blades of the helicopter. It was found that their mechanical, processing and thermal properties were remarkably improved and met completely the requirements of the structure design and forming technique of the composite rotor blade.

The research resin system of this work is suitable for various glass cloths, glass fibres and carbon fibre composites. Retention of the mechanical properties of these composites, especially at elevated temperature, appears excellent.

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Table 1 Property Comparison of Neat Resin System YEW-7808 and Its Various Fabric Composites *

Property	Resin casting	Uni. roving S-Glass	Uni. roving E-Glass	Twill weave cloth S-Glass	Plain weave cloth S-Glass	Carbon Fibre (Shanghai)
Mixed Viscosity, cps, 30°C	1200					
Gel Time, 80°C, h: min	2:14					
HDT, °C	186					
Tensile Strength, kg/mm ²	9.16	124	132	76.4	72.8	141
Tensile Modulus, kg/mm ²	364.2	4280	4124	3544	3212	11662
Tensile Elongation, %	4.4	2.4	2.6	3.2	3.4	2.1
Flexural Strength, kg/mm ²	13.2	132	136	78.1	75.2	147
Flexural Modulus, kg/mm ²	398.1	4411	4280	3652	3306	12105
Short Beam Shear Strength, kg/mm ²		9.48	9.60	6.55	6.46	11.2
Poisson's Ration		0.34	0.36	0.38	0.39	0.32

* Test Temperature 24 ± 2°C. Reinforcement Contents 70 ± 2%. Press cured 2h / 140°C

Table 2 Short Beam Shear Strength of Reinforced Research Epoxy Matrices * At Various Temperatures

Resin System	Glass %	Press Cured	Short Beam Shear Strength, kg/mm ²		
			30°C	120°C	150°C
YEW-7808 E-51 / W-95+HHPA / EMI-2.4	68.5	2h / 140°C	9.48	6.86	5.67
YEB-7912 E-51 / B-63+HHPA / EMI-2.4	69.4	2h / 140°C	9.06	5.94	4.30
YEN-8204 E-51 / CTBN+HHPA / EMI-2.4	70.2	2h / 140°C	8.42	4.22	3.56

* Reinforcement: S-glass twill weave woven cloth

Table 3 Flexural Properties of Research Matrix YEW-7808 Composites * At Various Temperatures

Property	Glass %	Press Cured	Test Temperature °C		
			30	120	150
Flexural Strength, kg/mm ²	68.4	2h / 140°C	132.4	102.2	--
	71.2		--	--	86.5
Flexural Modulus, kg/mm ²	68.4	2h / 140°C	4214	3792	--
	71.2		--	--	3471
Transverse Flexural Strength, kg/mm ²	70.6	2h / 140°C	16.8	13.4	11.0
Transverse Flexural Modulus, kg/mm ²	70.2	2h / 140°C	1872	1324	1086

* Reinforcement: S-glass unidirectional roving

Figure 1. The composite rotor blade structure and section

1. Erosion Strip, Titanium Alloy
2. Balance Weight, Plumbum
3. Spar, Roving Uni. Fiber: S-glass 72.5% (wt)
Resin: Epoxy system YEW-7808 27.5% (wt)
4. Core, PU Foam, Specific Weight 0.08
5. Back Edge, Roving Uni. Fiber: Carbon (Shanghai) 70% (wt)
Resin: Epoxy System YEB-7912 30% (wt)
6. Skin, Fabric $\pm 45^\circ$ Cloth: S-glass, twill weave 65% (wt)
Resin: Epoxy System YEW 7808 35% (wt)

Figure 2. The infrared absorbance spectra of the products of HHPA, EMI-2.4 cured epoxy resin at different temperatures. A: sample was heated at 150°C for 1 hour; B: sample was heated at 120°C for 1 hour; C: uncured epoxy resin

Figure 3. The effect of three modified agents on flexural strength of the research resin casting

Figure 4. The bending fatigue S-N curves of the composite for helicopter rotor blade

--- 50% Mod-Value Fatigue Plot
 — 99.9% Working Fatigue Plot
 1,3—Blade body
 2,4—Blade Root

GENERAL APPLICATIONS
